

INTELLIGENT ASSESSMENT MODEL TO INVESTIGATE MENTAL HEALTH: A PLS-SEM & MACHINE LEARNING HYBRID APPROACH

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Abstract

Poor mental health conditions are now a serious global issue. Every year, several millions of people are victims of this, and many more endure it their entire lives. The World Health Organization (WHO) anticipates that one-third of women and one-fifth of men may develop severe depressive disorders in their lives. For this reason, employee mental health has become a serious concern since it is crucial to workplace productivity, morale, job satisfaction, team relationships, and overall organizational effectiveness. Prioritizing mental health fosters a healthy work environment, resulting in a more resilient and engaged team. This study proposes an assessment model to investigate mental health and analyze the key features that contribute to mental health concerns. This study combines partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) with machine learning (ML) to enhance their -cause-predictive and exploratory abilities. Coupling these two strategies improves the anticipated accuracy of research models. The methodology begins with using PLS-SEM to identify statistically significant features that impact mental health among 17 independent features and the identified features are “Depression”, “Job Satisfaction”, “Mental health benefits or care provided by the employer”, and “Personal history of a mental health disorder”. After identifying the features, they were treated as input for several ML algorithms such as Logistic Regression, KNN, Random Forest, Decision Tree, etc. Then, a comparative study showed that Random Forest outperforms all other algorithms with 90.26% accuracy. This research will be one of the first attempts to help many organizations maintain healthy mental health. This concept allows organizations to analyze their employees' mental health and take the required steps to care for them.

Keywords

PLS-SEM, Machine-Learning, Prediction, Factor Analysis, Mental Health.

Introduction

The rising frequency of mental health diseases has become a serious public health threat that affects millions of individuals worldwide and imposes enormous economic and social expenses (World Health Organization, 2017). Conventional mental health evaluation methods, such as medical professional interviews and self-report questionnaires, frequently do not have the required accuracy and flexibility to address the intricate nature of mental health disorders. (Kazdin, 2018). These approaches may be hindered by biases, individuality, and lack of ability to dynamically adjust to the changing nature of mental health symptoms.

In recent times, machine learning (ML) has gained a great deal of attention, and it has provided new opportunities for the enhancement of many types of predictive evaluations. As a result, ML applications are considered the early preventive method in case of mental health-related issues. For instance, Reddy, et al., (2018) applied different ML algorithms to identify mental stress among employees and identified significant factors that lead to mental stress. In their research, Random forest outperformed other algorithms with an accuracy of 75.13%. Giannakakis, et al., (2019) also employed ML algorithms to predict stress levels, where the author used heart rate variability (HRV) parameter to recognize stress. Pramanta, et al., (2016) applied pulse data as an input variable to identify stress. In this study, data was collected every five minutes, resulting in a 5-minute relaxation interval for the user. It is evident that many researchers have used machine learning to predict stress or mental health, but they have employed different input features, leaving a gap in identifying common, significant factors contributing to employee mental health. Additionally, there is a lack of an appropriate ML model that can work for any type of employee to predict their stress or mental health based on the aforementioned identified factor. To bridge these gaps, this study is designed to pursue the following objectives:

- Assessing employee mental stress based on a set of derived factors.

- Analyzing the factors through PLS-SEM to identify the significant factors influencing employee mental health.
- Creating a model utilizing those significant factors, to predict employee mental stress
- Finding the best model by applying different machine learning algorithms to predict employee mental stress.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is known as a powerful approach to factor analysis because of its ability to assess complex relationships between observable and latent variables. The use of SEM in several domains has been widely documented, offering a solid foundation for comprehending the complex interactions between factors. In this study, a PLS-SEM and ML combined hybrid model has been introduced. Initially, 17 factors have been finalized as independent factors from the extant literature including journals, conference papers, survey questionnaires, and expert input. Then, factor analysis is performed through PLS-SEM. Significant factors are determined that affect the employee's mental health and stress level. After that, these significant factors are treated as input in creating ML models using Python language to predict employee mental stress. The model proposed in this study can be used by companies and organizations worldwide to improve employee mental health. As the initial phase of this hybrid model identifies key factors, organizations can focus on those aspects. Additionally, the predictive model enables them to evaluate their employees' mental health status, allowing them to aid those in need. Thus far as we are aware, no study of this kind has been conducted in the field of employee mental health, making this study a unique contribution to the field and body of knowledge.

Methodology

Data Description

Data was gathered via an online survey from March 2024 to April 2024, with employees from different companies in Dhaka, Bangladesh. This dataset contains eighteen factors where seventeen factors are independent factors and one dependent factor and thirty-three items encompassing information from 139 employees. These items are related to the factors. In PLS-SEM, items are the observable variables or indicators used for evaluating latent constructs, also known as factors. The measurement model establishes the link between items and factors, with items reflecting or forming the latent constructs. Exhibit 1 describes all the factors with their respective scale.

Exhibit 1. Factors Details.

SL.	Factors Name	Description	Scale
1	Company Type	Whether the company is tech or not?	Yes=1, No=0
2	Employee Age	Age of employee	Age in years
3	Employee Gender	Male or Female	Male=1, Female=0
4	Company Size	What is the company size in terms of employees? Where small=1-49, Medium=50-250, Big=250+	small=0, Medium=1, Big=2
5	Department	In which department the employee works tech or non-tech?	Tech=1, non-tech=0
6	Months with the Company	Working period with the company	months
7	Job-related Anxiety	Does the employee have any anxiety? Which is caused by his/her job and what is the level of it.	1-21
8	Bullying	Does the employee face any kind of bullying in the office	Yes=1, No=0
9	Depression	What is your depression severity? Where minimal depression= 1-4, mild depression= 5-9, moderate depression=10-14, moderately severe depression=15-19, severe depression=20-27	0-27
10	Job Satisfaction	Is the employee fully satisfied with his/her job?	Yes=1, No=0
11	Work-Life Balance	Does the employee have enough time for his personal life after the job?	Yes=1, No=0
12	Social Support	Does the employee have a supporting team and colleagues at his workplace?	Yes=1, No=0
13	Organizational Commitment	Is the employee committed to his/her company?	Yes=1, No=0

14	Family History of Mental Health Disorder	Does the employee’s family have any mental health disorder history?	Yes=1, No=0
15	Personal History of Mental Health Disorder	Does the employee have any mental health disorder history?	Yes=1, No=0
16	Mental Health Benefits of Care Provided by Employer	Does the company provide any kind of Mental Health Benefits?	Yes=1, No=0
17	Can discussing mental health with an employer backfire??	Will discussing mental health concerns with an employer have negative consequences?	Yes=1, No=0
18	<i>Perceived Stress</i>	<i>Is the employee currently feeling any stress?</i>	<i>Yes=1, No=0</i>

Proposed Framework

The suggested employee mental health prediction framework is comprised of eight steps. The first four phases are associated with PLS_SEM, followed by the ML model containing the remaining four phases. The steps are shown in Exhibit 2. The description of the steps is mentioned below:

- Step 1:** A literature review is done to create a list of significant factors.
- Step 2:** Create a questionnaire that includes the Likert scale
- Step 3:** Data was collected by circulating the questionnaire via email and collecting responses from employees of different companies.
- Step 4:** Conduct PLS-SEM factor analysis to identify and recognize critical factors within the collected data.
- Step 5:** Preprocess selected critical factors for data analysis and ensure accuracy, consistency, and quality in the dataset.
- Step 6:** Apply ML algorithms to the model, using recognized critical input factors.
- Step 7:** Analyze results using performance metrics
- Step 8:** Compare ML algorithms to find the best.

Exhibit 2. Steps of Proposed Framework of the Study.

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

SEM initially was developed by Sewall Wright in 1921, which is a valuable method for analyzing the causal link between latent and indicator variables, through both reflecting and formative manner (Pearl, 2012). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) is a statistical method. Unlike standard SEM, PLS-SEM is appropriate for assessing complicated models with limited sample sizes and non-normal data (Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2021).

Performance Metrics of PLS-SEM

Several parameters can be used in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to rank and assess the importance of factors (latent variables) influencing a dependent variable. Here are the main parameters:

Path Coefficients (β): These coefficients demonstrate the significance and trajectory of correlations between latent variables (Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2021). Higher absolute numbers suggest more robust correlations. Path coefficients with absolute values larger than 0.2 are frequently regarded as significant, with higher values (e.g., >0.3 or >0.5) suggesting stronger correlations whereas negative values indicate negative relationships.

Significance Levels (p-values) of Path Coefficients: These represent how statistically significant the path coefficients are (Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2021). p-values less than 0.05 usually suggest that the association is statistically significant. Factors with significant path coefficients (lower p-values) are regarded as more significant.

Machine Learning Algorithms

The description of each of the four machine-learning algorithms that were applied to construct the model is provided below:

1. Logistic Regression (LR): Logistic regression is a linear model commonly used for binary classification issues. It predicts the likelihood that an instance is associated with a specific class (Stoltzfus, 2011).

$$y = \frac{e^{(b_0+b_1x)}}{1+e^{(b_0+b_1x)}} \quad (1)$$

where,

- x = input variable
- y = anticipated outcome
- b_0 = term of bias or intercept
- b_1 = coefficient of input (x)

2. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): KNN relies on a distance metric. The accuracy of the classification improves as the metric better captures label similarity. There are multiple distance measures available such as Euclidean and Manhattan (Peterson, 2009). In this study, the Euclidean distance measure was used.

$$d(x, y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2} \quad [Euclidean\ distance] \quad (2)$$

$$d(x, y) = (\sum_{i=1}^m |X_i - Y_i|) \quad [Manhattan\ Distance] \quad (3)$$

3. Random Forest (RF): The random forest model is a mathematical model that generates predictions by combining assessments from multiple base models (Biau & Scornet, 2016). It is a type of ensemble method that consists of multiple decision trees. The model builds each tree based on a random selection of the data and characteristics. The ultimate prediction is typically determined by averaging or taking the majority vote of the predictions made by each tree.

$$B(x) = f_0(x) + f_1(x) + f_2(x) + \dots \quad (4)$$

4. Decision Tree (DT): A decision tree is a supervised machine-learning approach that constantly separates data depending on a parameter (Charbuty & Abdulazeez, 2021). The tree can be described in terms of two entities: decision nodes and leaves. The leaves represent the conclusions, while the data is split at the decision nodes.

Input Variable: A variable input effect is a system parameter that affects the system's performance as listed in items 1-17 in exhibit 1 in achieving the desired output response (perceived response). It is an item that the research alters

based on specific criteria. It is a research object that acts in accordance with established parameters. In this model, the input variables are the major factors discovered by PLS-SEM factor analysis.

Response Variable: A response variable is often referred to as the dependent variable. It is the one who produces the outcomes. In this paradigm, the response variable is perceived as stress.

Data Preprocessing

Missing values, outliers, and duplicates are regularly found in datasets created from real-world data, either by intention or by mistake. The input dataset must be cleansed, sanitized, updated, normalized, and feature-reduced before it is fed into the machine learning algorithm.

Exhibit 3. Feature Correlation Showing Relation Between Features.

In this study, during data preprocessing the null value was checked, there was no null value or missing value. Duplicated values were checked and removed. There was no outlier. During data collection, employees filled in 1 and 0, where 1 means 'yes' and 0 means 'no'. The varied scales within this dataset necessitated scaling, achieved through the utilization of the StandardScaler function. Four significant factors were identified using PLS-SEM factor analysis prior to data preprocessing and model creation. According to the proposed framework, data preprocessing and model inputs will focus exclusively on these four factors. From Exhibit 3, the feature correlation chart, it can be said that all the input variables are well related with the output. This feature correlation also puts the weight of PLS-SEM feature analysis as the PLS-SEM also showed the same result.

Performance Metrics

Performance matrices are considered essential tools that are used for the systematic evaluation and improvement of performance. Measurable indicators, benchmarks, and targets are utilized in matrices to provide a structured method for evaluating performance, enabling firms to make well-informed decisions, promote ongoing improvement, and ultimately reach their strategic goals. The performance metrics utilized encompass *accuracy*, *recall*, *precision*, and *F1* score.

Accuracy - The percentage of correctly classified outcomes is calculated by dividing them by the predicted outcomes (Khan, et al., 2024).

$$Accuracy = (TP + TN)/(TP + TN + FP + FN) \tag{5}$$

Here,

- TP = True Positive
- TN = True Negative
- FP = False Positive
- FN = False Negative

Recall - The proportion of positive events predicted accurately by the model is measured (Khan, et al., 2023).

$$Recall = TP/(TP + FN) \tag{6}$$

Precision - The proportion of outcomes that are accurately recognized as positive among all outcomes predicted as positive by the model is marked. (Liu, et al., 2014).

$$Precision = TP/(TP + FP) \tag{7}$$

F1 Score - The harmonic mean of accuracy and memory balances their trade-offs. (Liu, et al., 2014).

$$F1\ Score = (2 * Precision * Recall)/(Precision + Recall) \tag{8}$$

Results Analysis

PLS-SEM Modelling

Exhibit 4 shows the model structure of the PLS-SEM model. It can be seen that in this model there is only one dependent variable which is perceived stress. This dependent variable directly depends on seventeen independent variables. This model also clearly shows the most significant factors by highlighting their path coefficient.

Exhibit 4. PLS-SEM Model.

Exhibit 4, shows the path coefficient β and P values for each factor. In the case of the path coefficient higher absolute numbers suggest more robust correlations and for p-value less than 0.05 usually suggests that the association is statistically significant. Taking these two conditions into account, it is evident from exhibit 4 & exhibit 5 that there are four significant factors for the dependent variable "Perceived Stress.". These factors are "Depression", "Job Satisfaction", "Mental health benefits or care provided by the employer", and "Personal history of a mental health disorder".

Exhibit 5. PLS-SEM Result Analysis.

	Path coefficients (β)	P values
Bullying -> Perceived Stress	0.122	0.391
Company Size -> Perceived Stress	0.055	0.379
Company Type -> Perceived Stress	0.132	0.368
Department -> Perceived Stress	-0.007	0.946
Depression -> Perceived Stress	0.377	0.003
Do you think Discussing Mental Health Issues with the Employer can have Negative Consequences? -> Perceived Stress	0.07	0.306
Employee Age -> Perceived Stress	-0.011	0.859
Employee Gender -> Perceived Stress	-0.024	0.851
Family history of mental health disorders -> Perceived Stress	0.132	0.062
Job Satisfaction -> Perceived Stress	0.261	0.046
Job-related Anxiety -> Perceived Stress	0.146	0.23
Mental health benefits or care provided by the employer -> Perceived Stress	-0.286	0.026
Months with Company -> Perceived Stress	-0.051	0.247
Organizational Commitment -> Perceived Stress	0.12	0.364
Personal history of a mental health disorder -> Perceived Stress	0.342	0
Social Support -> Perceived Stress	0.066	0.643
Work-Life Balance -> Perceived Stress	-0.149	0.122

Machine Learning Modelling

Following PLS-SEM factor analysis, four important components were identified as significant predictors of employee mental stress. These parameters served as inputs for predictive machine learning models. Exhibit 6 shows the input and output variables for ML models.

Exhibit 6. Performance Metrics of the Models.

Input Variable	Output Variable
Depression	Perceived Stress
Job Satisfaction	
Mental health benefits or care provided by the employer	
Personal history of a mental health disorder	

The performance of the four ML models was evaluated by comparing their parameters. Exhibit 7 shows the recall, precision, F1 score, and accuracy of each ML method employed in this research.

Exhibit 7. Performance Metrics of the Models.

	Logistic Regression (LR)	K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	Random Forest (RF)	Decision Tree (DT)
Accuracy (%)	81.74	86.50	90.26	88.14
Precision (%)	82.38	85.14	92.13	88.00
F1 (%)	81.40	86.29	88.78	87.13
Recall (%)	82.90	86.42	89.10	88.15

Exhibit 7 shows that random forest is the best-fitted model among all other models in predicting employee mental stress. The table shows that the testing values for random forest accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores are 90.26%, 92.13%, 89.10%, and 88.78%, respectively. The accuracy of 90.26% demonstrates that the model can properly estimate employee mental stress in more than 90.26% of cases which is higher than the rest of the models. The F1 score of RFs is 88.78%, which indicates that the model has a high level of recall and precision whereas the F1 values of KNN, DT, and LR are 86.29%, 87.13%, and 81.40%, respectively. In this study, recall score is regarded as the primary criterion for performance evaluation. This is because, in a healthcare dataset, it is vital to identify each positive patient without missing a single positive instance (Gupta, Anand, & Hasija, 2021). The ML model with the best recall score lowers the value of false negatives and false positives. A low false positive score indicates fewer stress-positive situations when the employee is negative. Similarly, a lower false negative suggests a lesser likelihood of a stress-related negative result when is positive. In this comparative study, the values of performance metrics of other algorithms such as KNN, DT, and LR clearly show that random forest is the best model.

Managerial Implications and Conclusion

This study primarily listed a set of important factors from previous research, different questionnaires, and expert input. Subsequently, a questionnaire was developed to conduct an online survey of employees from various companies to collect the data, after that PLS-SEM factor analysis was performed to find out the most significant factors that directly impact the employee's mental stress. After factor analysis, the result showed that the most critical factors are "Depression", "Job Satisfaction", "Mental health benefits or care provided by the employer", and "Personal history of a mental health disorder". After successfully recognizing the impactful factors. These factors were treated as input variables for creating a machine-learning model. Then data preprocessing was performed. After that four different algorithms were applied. Through performance evaluation, random forest was the most fitted one. With this model, an employee's mental health can be assessed with great accuracy. This will help companies and organizations all over the world to take really good care of their employee's mental health. And with mentally healthy employees, companies can flourish. The following are the study's main implications:

- This study identifies the significant factors for employee mental health, this will help different companies to take extra care of these factors to keep the employees mentally healthy.
- This study shows that random forest provides the most accurate prediction among the four algorithms while combined with the PLS-SEM model.
- The step-by-step PLS-SEM & ML Hybrid method discussed in this study can also be applied at a national and individual level to predict the stress of employees.

In addition to medical implications, our approach has some managerial implications as well. The following are the primary implications from a management standpoint.

- Implementing this strategy will help mental health physicians and specialists be more accurate and faster, allowing hospital administration to give treatment more effectively and efficiently.
- Hospital Management can be financially beneficial with the help of this model, as with this model they will require less time to attend to patients so they will be able to attend to more patients than usual.

To maximize the effectiveness of an "Intelligent Assessment Model to Investigate Mental Health," companies need to define clear objectives and goals for its implementation, such as identifying mental health trends and providing targeted support. In addition to ensuring data privacy and confidentiality, it is important to train HR and management on how to use the model and interpret its results sensitively. By integrating the model with existing HR systems, data collection and analysis will be streamlined. An initial assessment can provide a baseline for identifying areas of concern and tailoring interventions accordingly. The continuous feedback and evaluation process will allow for continual improvement, while establishing a supportive organizational culture will encourage open communication and reduce stigma in the mental health community.

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